

D3.7: Solutions for Security Testing of Low-Level System Components (first version)

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the first version of the RESCALE solutions that target security testing of low-level system components. Specifically, we outline the features, functionalities, and architecture of the core solutions developed within Task 3.4. Our solutions focus on both software and hardware vulnerabilities that affect low-level system components. On the software side, we introduce SafeFetch, a solution to detect and mitigate double-fetch vulnerabilities—common issues in low-level system components. We also introduce FATex, a solution to perform firmware analysis for the purpose of security testing. On the hardware side, we present InSpectre Gadget, a solution to identify and analyze the exploitability of Spectre-type vulnerabilities, which remain a significant and poorly understood attack surface for low-level system components.

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Internal Reviewers

1. Tzortzia Koutsouri - (CBRL)
2. Nassos Bountioulos - (CBRL)
3. Narges Yousefnezhad - (BNR)
4. Andrei Costin - (BNR)

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List of Abbreviations

- AST** Abstract Syntax Tree. 39
- BHB** Branch History Buffer. 32, 33
- BHI** Branch History Injection. 30–34
- BTB** Branch Target Buffer. 31, 32
- BTI** Branch Target Injection. 30, 31
- CLI** Command Line Interface. 28
- CPU** Central Processing Unit. 30–34, 38
- CSV** Comma Separated Values. 28
- CSV2** Cache Speculation Variant 2. 31
- CVE** Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures. 31
- DSCG** Dynamic Supply Chain component Guarantee. 8, 10, 28, 43
- eBPF** Extended Berkeley Packet Filter. 30–34
- eIBRS** Enhanced Indirect Branch Restricted Speculation. 30, 31, 33, 34
- FAT** Firmware Analysis Toolkit. 27
- FATex** Firmware Analysis toolkit extended. 28, 29
- FineIBT** Fine-Grained Indirect Branch Tracking. 30, 34
- HTML** HyperText Markup Language. 28
- IBT** Indirect Branch Tracking. 30, 33, 34
- IoT** Internet of Things. 28
- JSON** JavaScript Object Notation. 28
- MMU** Virtual Memory Area. 12, 16
- OS** Operating System. 12
- PTE** Page Table Entry. 13
- QEMU** Quick Emulator. 27, 29
- SLAM** Spectre based on Leaky Address Masking. 38

SMAP Supervisor Mode Access Prevention. 13

SMEP Supervisor Mode Execution Prevention. 13

SMT Simultaneous Multithreading. 38

TBOM Trusted Bill of Materials. 28

TCB Trusted Computing Base. 15

TLB Translation Lookaside Buffer. 38

TOCTTOU Time-Of-Check To Time-Of-Use. 12, 14

VMA Virtual Memory Area. 16, 17

XSS Cross-Site Scripting. 28

1 Introduction

To complement the core static and dynamic analysis solutions developed in Task 3.1 and Task 3.2, respectively, as well as the physical side-channel leakage analyzer developed in Task 3.3, Task 3.4 focuses on developing solutions for security testing of low-level system components. These solutions emphasize program analysis and instrumentation of low-level systems software, such as operating systems kernels, to find low-level vulnerabilities and analyze their impact. As part of the overall RESCALE platform, these solutions perform hardware/software attack surface analysis and generate reports contributing to the generation of the Dynamic Supply Chain Component Guarantee (DSCG) (whose foundation is described in D3.3).

1.1 Scope & Contribution

This document outlines the outcomes of the first phase of Task 3.4, *Low-Level System Security Testing*. This phase encompasses the initial design of the solutions for security testing of low-level system components. Our focus is on the core solutions targeting both software and hardware vulnerabilities that affect low-level system components on commodity platforms. The document is based on two papers developed within the RESCALE project and presented at the 2024 USENIX Security Symposium [73, 28].

1.2 Relation to Work Packages, Deliverables, and Activities

Deliverable D3.7 results from Task 3.4 within Work Package 3 (WP3) and is also relevant to Work Packages 4 (WP4) and 5 (WP5). This deliverable details the design of the solutions for low-level system security testing, including specific integration aspects related to WP5.

1.3 Contribution to WP3 and Project Objectives

Deliverable D3.7, which documents our progress in Task 3.4, aligns with WP3 Objective O3.5 to provide a platform for performing security tests for low-level software and processor implementations. Additionally, it contributes to Project Objective O2 by analyzing microarchitectural attacks.

1.4 Document Structure

This section outlines the structure of the deliverable as follows:

- **Section 2** provides a high-level overview of the solutions for security testing of low-level system components.

- **Section 3** details the design of SafeFetch, our solution for detecting and mitigating double-fetch (software) vulnerabilities. These vulnerabilities frequently affect low-level system components, such as operating system kernels.
- **Section 4** presents FATex, our solution for analyzing firmware, with support for static and dynamic firmware analysis for the purpose of security testing.
- **Section 5** describes the design of InSpectre Gadget, our solution for detecting and analyzing Spectre-type (hardware) vulnerabilities. These vulnerabilities represent an increasingly large attack surface for low-level system components.
- **Section 6** summarizes and concludes the deliverable.

2 High-level Solution Overview

The goal of Task 3.4 is to develop the Low-level Hardware Assessment component part of the RESCALE platform. This component provides security testing solutions for low-level system targets. More specifically, this (standalone) component performs program analysis of a given low-level program binary. Given an input binary provided by the analyst (used interchangeably here with the term Consumer in the context of RESCALE), the component outputs a report with the attack surface analysis for the intended vulnerabilities. The Low-level Hardware Assessment component can seamlessly integrate with CI/CD pipelines (e.g., automatically triggering scans at each code change and immediately uncovering new vulnerabilities). The component complements the other components of the dynamic testing module and its output contributes to the overall DSCG report established in Task 3.2 and presented in D3.3.

For the development of the Low-level Hardware Assessment component, our investigation focuses on fundamental low-level system targets such as operating system kernels, hypervisors, or firmware. Given their central role in IT operations, these are prime targets for attackers seeking to exploit low-level vulnerabilities for purposes such as data exfiltration, unauthorized access, or broader system compromise.

As far as the vulnerabilities are concerned, we focus on high-impact low-level vulnerabilities in both software and hardware. On the software vulnerability side, we focus on vulnerabilities that specifically target low-level system components, double-fetch vulnerabilities in particular. These vulnerabilities occur when a memory location is read multiple times without proper synchronization and/or sanitization and are widespread in privileged software such as operating system kernels or hypervisors. Moreover, the impact of double-fetch vulnerabilities on low-level system components is substantial: attackers armed with these vulnerabilities can exploit race conditions to manipulate data between reads and ultimately escalate privileges.

On the hardware vulnerability side, we focus on microarchitectural vulnerabilities, and Spectre-type vulnerabilities in particular. These vulnerabilities have recently gained significant momentum due to their pervasive impact on modern processors. Indeed, Spectre exploits speculative execution, a pervasive microarchitectural optimization adopted by all the modern high-performance CPUs. Moreover, the impact of Spectre attacks on low-level system components is, again, substantial: Spectre-enabled attackers can leak arbitrary data from the victim software. And, since low-level system software such as operating system kernels or hypervisors have access to the entirety of physical memory on the system, attackers can ultimately leak arbitrary data stored in physical memory.

To address these vulnerabilities, we present three core solutions developed within Task 3.4. For double-fetch vulnerabilities, we present SafeFetch, a solution to efficiently detect double-fetch vulnerabilities in privileged software. Specifically SafeFetch can not only automatically detect potential instances of these vulnerabilities, but can also efficiently mitigate them as they occur to completely close the attack surface. While our design is general, our current solution specifically targets double-fetch vulnerabilities in operating system kernels and thus possibly triggered by a malicious user process. At the firmware level, we also present FATex, a generic platform to perform firmware analysis for the purpose of security testing.

For Spectre-type vulnerabilities, we present InSpectre Gadget, a tool to operate Spectre attack surface analysis for software susceptible to a Spectre threat model. Specifically, InSpectre

Gadget can not only automatically detect Spectre-type vulnerabilities by means of program analysis, but can also reason about their exploitability characteristics and thus their severity. While our design is general, our current solution specifically targets Spectre-v2 vulnerabilities in operating system kernels or hypervisors.

3 SafeFetch

The operating system (OS) kernel is the bedrock of modern systems. To provide service, the kernel includes a syscall interface, an explicit boundary between *untrusted* OS processes and the *trusted* kernel. Hence, it is crucial for the kernel to properly sanitize data that flows through this boundary (e.g., syscall arguments). Failure to do so may lead to (kernel) **double-fetch bugs** [8]. Such bugs occur when the kernel fetches (i.e., reads) the same/overlapping data from user space twice—a common kernel design pattern—without properly (re)sanitizing data on the second fetch. In essence, double-fetch bugs introduce a race condition, which attackers can exploit to mount *time-of-check to time-of-use* (TOCTTOU) attacks—changing user data between the two fetches. This is to bypass sanity checks and typically escalate privileges. Such bugs are both common (as they involve skipping seemingly “redundant” kernel checks [8]) and elusive (as they normally escape testing with production sanitizers [40]).

Prior research [71, 39, 63, 78] has mostly sought to statically detect and report several double-fetch bugs [19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24]. However, prior detection tools are imprecise and thus unsuitable to detect and mitigate double-fetch bugs in production. More recently, Midas [8] proposed the first solution to offer both detection and protection guarantees against double-fetch bugs. Midas relies on the MMU and copy-on-write mechanics to expose consistent snapshots of user pages to each syscall. To this end, Midas traps writes to each fetched user page, copies the page, and exposes the new (old) page to the writer (syscall). While this approach detects double fetches and also structurally prevents double-fetch exploitation, it also incurs nontrivial overhead due to the cost of trapping, remapping, and copying pages as well as operating at the coarse page granularity (causing overtrapping and overcopying due to *false sharing* [8]). Finally, due to the complex and costly operations Midas whitelists a number of syscalls (including the kernel-fetch heavy `execve`), ultimately reducing protection coverage.

To address these issues, we implement SafeFetch, a practical detection and protection system for kernel double-fetch bugs. The key idea is to move the core instrumentation from writes to kernel fetches, with the kernel maintaining per-syscall *caches* to serve kernel fetches. Indeed, our design has been inspired by Linux kernel developers seeking a practical double-fetch bug mitigation by “*performing some kind of kernel-side caching of user space memory*” [45]. SafeFetch’s design prevents concurrent (attacker-controlled) writes from corrupting data exposed to kernel double fetches—which instead hit the previously populated kernel-fetch cache by construction. We found that the vast majority of syscalls only copy a few bytes from user space, hence caching kernel-fetch data per-syscall can be done in a *simple* and *inexpensive* way. In contrast to Midas’ *write-side* instrumentation strategy, SafeFetch’s *fetch-side* strategy eliminates the need for costly MMU-based instrumentation (as writes run uninstrumented), false sharing and overcopying (as the cache operates at the byte rather than page granularity), and syscall-based whitelisting (as individual problematic kernel fetches can be whitelisted as needed). As a result, SafeFetch significantly improves both the performance and the security (protection coverage) of state-of-the-art solutions at a fraction of the complexity.

Contributions

We make the following contributions:

- We investigate common kernel fetch patterns during syscall execution and use the resulting insights to design a per-syscall kernel-fetch cache.
- We present SafeFetch, an implementation of our design to structurally mitigate *double-fetch* bugs in the Linux kernel. We show SafeFetch can be seamlessly integrated into existing kernel code paths, resulting in a practical implementation.

3.1 Background

This section provides background information on user/kernel memory isolation and double-fetch bugs.

User/kernel Memory Isolation

Modern operating systems rely on virtual memory support to enforce user/kernel memory isolation, that is preventing user (kernel) execution from accessing kernel (user) memory. This is typically done by using a joint virtual memory address space—where both user and kernel memory mappings coexist during user/kernel execution—and features offered by modern memory management units to enforce isolation. Specifically, on x86 platforms, the kernel can set (unset) the User/Supervisor bit each Page Table Entry (PTE) for user (kernel) memory mappings. This prevents user execution from accessing kernel memory. It also prevents the reverse (i.e., kernel execution accessing user memory) assuming Supervisor Mode Access/Execution Prevention features (SMAP and SMEP, respectively) are enabled.

While important for memory isolation, SMAP complicates the implementation of common operations such as *kernel fetches*, that is user-to-kernel data transfers often issued by the kernel as part of syscall handling (e.g., copying a message from user memory to be sent over the network). To ease their implementation, modern operating systems typically support special kernel *transfer functions* in order to safely transfer data between user and kernel. For example, the Linux kernel offers two user-to-kernel (i.e., `copy_from_user` and `get_user`) and two kernel-to-user (i.e., `copy_to_user` and `put_user`) transfer functions, which temporarily disable SMAP and copy data from/to user memory (respectively).

Double-fetch Bugs

A kernel *double fetch* occurs in presence of kernel fetches transferring the same user data twice, that is with multiple user-to-kernel transfer function invocations for the same (or overlapping) user data on Linux. This pattern is normally benign and used to simplify or optimize common types of (e.g., deep or variable-length [71]) user-to-kernel data transfers. However, if the kernel assumes the data to be invariant and only validates data on the first fetch, the second fetch originates a *double-fetch bug*. Such bugs are particularly insidious as they introduce a race condition that may never cause any harm during normal execution. However, an attacker can exploit such bugs by racing against kernel execution from another user thread and corrupting the (unsanitized) data exposed to the second fetch. Such *time-of-check to time-of-use* (TOCTTOU) attack can bypass sanity checks and often kickstart a privilege escalation exploit [71].

Figure 1: Workflow of a double-fetch exploit.

Figure 1 depicts the workflow of a typical double-fetch exploit. In response to *Thread 1* executing a syscall, the kernel first fetches and validates some user *@data*. Shortly after, another attacker-controlled *Thread 2* concurrently modifies the *@data* in user space. In *Thread 1*, the kernel then proceeds to fetch *@data* again without (re)validation. This allows the attacker to bypass validation checks and mount a TOCTTOU attack. Prior work has largely focused on *detecting* such bugs with reasonable accuracy [71, 39, 63, 78]. We instead focus on both detecting and mitigating double fetches, while proposing a much simpler and more efficient design than the state-of-the-art protection system [8].

3.2 Threat Model

We assume a typical local exploitation threat model, with an unprivileged user-space attacker seeking to exploit a kernel double-fetch bug. Other classes of vulnerabilities are out of scope, e.g., addressed by orthogonal mitigations. The attacker ultimately aims to mount a TOCTTOU attack for many different purposes, e.g., privilege escalation, info leak, denial of service, etc.

3.3 Overview

To hinder exploitation of kernel double-fetch bugs, SafeFetch guarantees that, during the lifetime of each syscall, kernel fetches to the same user data will return the same value. To this end, SafeFetch caches data read by kernel fetches at the per-thread and per-syscall granularity, as illustrated in Figure 2. As shown in the figure, when a syscall fetches some user *@data* for the first time, SafeFetch proxies the fetch to user memory and stores the fetched data in a per-

Figure 2: SafeFetch hindering a double-fetch exploit.

thread in-kernel cache. When the syscall fetches the same `@data` again, SafeFetch retrieves the data from the cache. As such, double fetches are always consistently served with the initial version of the data regardless of any concurrent updates to user memory. At the end of the syscall lifecycle, the cache is invalidated to implement per-syscall caching semantics.

Internally, SafeFetch includes two core components, as shown in Figure 3. The Cache Frontend intercepts each kernel fetch, i.e., (user-to-kernel) transfer function invocation, and returns a *sanitized* range (i.e., a contiguous, immutable user memory block) in output. To this end, the frontend queries the current *syscall cache* for the range. In case of a hit, a (sub)range is served directly from the cache. In case of a miss, the frontend notifies the Cache Backend. The latter provisions the cache to store the missing (sub)range (fetched from user memory) by means of a *custom allocator*.

Challenges

While SafeFetch’s design is conceptually simple, there are several challenges involved in its realization. First, the need for an in-kernel cache may lead to a nontrivial TCB impact, affecting security. However, we found it is feasible to efficiently implement our design with small TCB impact. Second, the need to interpose on all fetch operations may lead to protection coverage (and thus security) issues. However, we found it is feasible to produce a (nearly) full-coverage

Figure 3: SafeFetch’s high-level architecture.

implementation on modern operating systems such as Linux, faring even better than the state of the art (Midas). Third, our fetch-side instrumentation strategy may end up copying more data than Midas’ write-side strategy in case user data is never changed during syscall execution. However, we found that such cost is marginal compared to that of MMU-based instrumentation, resulting in better performance. Finally, our design require instrumenting the kernel’s fast path (i.e., transfer functions). As such, its instrumentation and data structures need to be carefully designed to efficiently support typical kernel fetch patterns. Nonetheless, we found it is possible to capture a variety of different fetch patterns with relatively simple data structures. In the next sections, we first analyze the patterns relevant to our design. Then, we use the insights gathered from our analysis to detail our design.

3.4 Profiling Kernel Fetches

While our syscall caches are superficially similar to other kernel caches since they may support similar range queries, our design requirements are fairly unique. For instance, the Virtual Memory Area (VMA) cache is a classic example of a kernel cache supporting range queries, however, its lookup patterns are wholly different from ours (lookups on locality-friendly memory management operations vs. lookups on kernel fetches) and so are its scope (process vs. syscall) and data storage requirements (fixed- vs. variable-sized data). As such, to make optimal design decisions, we need to learn more about typical patterns for kernel fetches, including

their frequency, data transfer size, etc.

To this end, we developed a simple profiler to gather kernel-fetch statistics. Specifically, our profiler interposes on syscall execution and records the following statistics: the total number of ranges a syscall transfers from user space, the average size of ranges transferred by a syscall, and the total amount of data a syscall fetches from user space. Moreover, for each process executed during profiling, we also gather the number of syscalls that transfer data from user space. We use various benchmarks (e.g., LMBench, OSBench) and popular user applications (e.g., Nginx, Apache) to generate a workload to sample syscall execution. In total, our workload generated around 317 million syscall samples, exercising 165 individual syscalls ($\approx 52\%$ of all defined syscalls for Linux x86.64). Our main profiling results are depicted in Figures 4, 5, 6, 7, 8. We elaborate on the results in the next sections, using the gathered insights to motivate our design.

3.5 Cache Frontend

To provide the kernel with a consistent view of user memory, the cache frontend interposes on all user-to-kernel *transfer* function invocations requesting a specific user range. In response, the frontend queries the syscall cache for the range by means of the user (virtual) address and the length of the range. After the query completes, the frontend performs a query resolution step, fetching parts of the range from user space into the cache if needed (i.e., if not cached) and then forwarding a sanitized range to the original transfer function.

The frontend considers a user range A *sanitized* if and only if: for any sub-range B of contiguous user addresses, such that $B \subseteq A$, and B was previously fetched during the execution of the syscall (i.e., via a previous transfer function) then B must consist of the same bytes as when it was first fetched. When querying the cache, the frontend uses a predetermined *search policy* to locate the range in the cache. The search policy is subject to the (meta)data structure used to bookkeep the user ranges in the cache.

3.5.1 Efficient Range Queries

Given a user start and end address (i.e., a range) SafeFetch needs to find all cached chunks that overlap with this input range. Since a range may only partially overlap with an existing range (or multiple cached ranges), we are interested in finding the optimal data structure that can service this operation efficiently. For this purpose, other kernel subsystems use either linked lists (for small caches) or red-black trees (for large caches). The Virtual Memory Area (VMA) cache is case in point, generally serving address range queries via a per-process red-black tree. However, the VMA cache's fast path uses a linked list for the few recently used VMAs.

We experimented with both types of data structures in the context of SafeFetch. In both cases, a node contains *metadata* recording the start/end address of the range and a reference to the cached *data*. Clearly, in the case of many cached ranges, we expect linked-list-based queries to perform poorly, with a worst-case search complexity of $O(n)$. In the same vein, we expect red-black trees to be more efficient, with a worst-case search complexity of $O(\log(n))$ due to constant-time rebalancing. Indeed, we experimentally verified that after around 100 cached ranges, the average search time of a linked list is slowed down by a factor of two compared to a

Figure 4: Percentage of syscall samples vs. number of ranges they fetch.

red-black tree. However, when the cache contains only a few elements we observed the linked list significantly outperforming a red-black tree. On top of more lightweight search logic, a small linked list has another important performance edge over a small red-black tree on the insertion path (i.e., when adding a new user range into the cache). Indeed, due to rebalancing, insertions in the red-black tree are always around 10 orders of magnitude slower than in a linked list. Since according to our profiling results, double fetches are rare (occurring once every 1,277 sampled syscalls), insertions are frequent and are thus important to consider for performance.

Selecting the ideal data structure

To select the ideal candidate between our two data structures, we turn to our profiling results. Figure 4 shows the percentage of syscall samples that fetch N ranges from user memory across all the profiled benchmarks. As shown in the figure, most samples ($\approx 64\%$) do not fetch user ranges at all, while the vast majority of those which do, fetch at most one range ($\approx 28.7\%$ of samples). Even so, a nontrivial number of samples ($\approx 7.32\%$) fetch at most 30 ranges, while only $\approx 0.06\%$ samples fetch over 30 ranges. As our results suggest, a (small) linked list seems the ideal candidate to support range queries for the vast majority of syscall samples. However, we also observed samples fetching as many as $\approx 4,000$ ranges. In those cases, the linked list has very poor performance and the red-black tree is a vastly better option.

To optimize for all possible syscall scenarios, we ultimately opted for an adaptive search policy. In other words, the search policy uses a linked list by default until the number of ranges in the cache reaches a predetermined threshold. When the threshold is exceeded, SafeFetch switches to a red-black tree implementation. To convert the linked list into a red-black tree, SafeFetch uses an efficient algorithm that constructs a balanced red-black tree from an ordered linked list. This is done by first copying the pointers to ranges in a vector and then iterating over the vector in a binary breath-first search fashion. To keep the algorithm efficient, we need to initiate the conversion when the list contains a number of ranges of the form $2^N - 1$.

3.5.2 Query Resolution

When processing the result of the query, the Cache Frontend makes different decisions depending on whether it found a cached user range colliding with the queried range (**cache hit**) or not (**cache miss**).

In case of a miss, no subrange from the queried range was previously fetched from user space. As a resolution, the frontend fetches the range from user space and instructs the backend to allocate storage to insert the range into the cache. It then also indexes the new range by inserting new metadata into the linked list or red-black tree with with $O(1)$ complexity—by piggybacking on the result of the previous query.

Cache hits can either be *perfect* or *partial*. A perfect hit means that the frontend found a cached range which contains the entire range it queried for. In this case, the frontend forwards the same range from the cache without performing any fetch from user space. A cache hit is partial if the frontend finds a cached range that collides with the range it queried for, but does not contain the entire range. In this case, the queried range may collide with multiple cached ranges previously fetched from user space and the frontend needs to first execute a range defragmentation step to determine the sanitized range. Let B be the queried range and let $M = \{A_i | A_i \in \text{cache} \wedge A_i \cap B \neq \emptyset\}$ containing all cached ranges that collide with B . Defragmentation involves computing a new range C such that $C = \cup_{i=1}^n A_i \cup (B \setminus \cup_{i=1}^n A_i)$. In other words, the defragmented range C contains all bytes from the cached ranges colliding with B , while the sub-ranges of bytes that are not cached yet are fetched from user space. The frontend instructs the backend to replace all colliding ranges in the cache with the newly defragmented range C , after which it can service the sanitized range from C . Defragmentation piggybacks on the result of the previous search, because all colliding ranges can be found by using the previous search's iterator. To support this, insertion in the linked list and red-black tree preserves the virtual address ordering of cached ranges.

3.6 Cache Backend

The Cache Backend is responsible with managing the backing memory for the syscall cache. Specifically, its main goals are to efficiently manage the lifecycle of ranges in the cache and exploit CPU cache locality as much as possible. The latter can be achieved by stacking together ranges in memory for data locality and thus better CPU cache utilization, which speeds up range queries. The former involves enforcing policies for range allocation/deallocation and storage provisioning/relinquishing techniques to keep cache operations optimal.

To achieve its goals, the backend maintains one cache for each in-transit syscall (at the per-thread granularity) and adheres to a cache organization specifically tailored to maximize data locality when performing range queries through the cache. Additionally, the backend enforces a series of range lifecycle management policies to efficiently oversee cache lifespan. To support this overall strategy, the backend relies on a custom memory allocator.

Figure 5: Percentage of syscall samples vs. average size of data they fetch.

3.6.1 Custom Allocator

A naive allocation policy would be to create an object in the cache every time a syscall fetches a new range, by using an of-the-shelf kernel allocator (e.g., slab) to accommodate range data and metadata. However, standard kernel allocators do not give control over where objects are placed in (virtual) memory, so we cannot assure locality to improve the performance of range queries. Moreover, for an off-the-shelf allocator the allocation and deallocation logic might cause non-trivial overhead when syscalls transfer many ranges from user space, which happens in practice (see Figure 4).

A better approach is to service kernel memory in larger chunks to fit multiple ranges, i.e., using a *region-based allocation* scheme [4]. In such a scheme, a *region* consists of one or more *buffers* (contiguous memory blocks) with the same data lifetime. In a region, memory objects are allocated one after another in memory (in the current buffer) and get deallocated all at once (by flushing all the buffers), once the lifetime of all the objects in the region ends. As such, region-based allocation allows us to pack ranges together in memory to improve locality. Moreover, it reduces the number of calls to the underlying allocator when allocating ranges. On the fast path, an allocation involves only bumping a pointer to the next slot in the current buffer. Finally, it can efficiently deallocate all the allocated objects in one blow.

SafeFetch uses a custom region-based allocator, which services kernel memory at the granularity of a region, every time the backend requests more storage to hold ranges. To understand how well SafeFetch can benefit from region allocation’s locality-friendly design, we turn again to our profiling results. Figure 5 shows the percentage of syscall samples that fetch an average size S of user data across all the profiled benchmarks. As shown in the figure, the majority (i.e., 65%) of syscall samples fetch ranges that are on average less than 64 bytes, confirming a high degree of data locality in a region in the common case. SafeFetch also benefits from the fast deallocation path of region-based allocation, efficiently deallocating all the ranges in the region when the syscall terminates. As an optimization, SafeFetch does not discard the buffers once the region is deallocated, but adds them to a pool for (fast) reuse in new regions created

Figure 6: Percentage of syscall samples vs. total amount of data they fetch.

by future syscalls.

The next question is the buffer size one should use. As Figure 5 suggests, small allocation requests are common suggesting small buffers are desirable. Moreover, Figure 6 shows the percentage of syscall samples that fetch a total amount of B bytes of user data across all the profiled benchmarks. As shown in the figure, although a moderate portion of syscalls transfer much data (even above 8 pages), the vast majority transfer far less than a page of data. As a result, SafeFetch uses a single 1-page buffer by default in each new region (syscall) and elastically adds buffers as needed in the edge cases—many fetches per syscall or fetches transferring over 4 KB of data.

3.6.2 Dual Region Design

A naive approach would be to store the user memory ranges and the metadata necessary for range queries as a standalone object in one single per-syscall region. However, this approach would lead to metadata fragmentation and poor locality because metadata would be intermixed with data bytes. While most fetched ranges are small, we saw that syscalls can transfer larger ranges as well (Figure 5). To maximize data locality for range querying, the Cache Backend partitions the syscall cache in two separate regions: a *data* region stores all byte ranges copied from user space while a *metadata* region stores the bear bone necessities to perform queries over ranges. Consequently, for each user range, the backend maintains two objects: a) a *data* object storing the range of bytes copied from user space and b) a *metadata* object storing the properties of the range used when querying (e.g., user virtual address, length, pointer to the data object, and a field used to link into a red-black tree or linked-list).

The size of *metadata* objects is fixed and small, allowing one to provision metadata regions with buffers smaller than a page. Nonetheless, we chose to serve 1-page buffers to metadata regions as well because this leads to better CPU cache coloring (and utilization) [44]. Despite the same default buffer size, the two regions provision their buffers from separate memory

Figure 7: Percentage of processes vs. number of syscalls fetching user data.

pools (i.e., slab caches) to further improve locality.

3.6.3 Lifecycle Management

Range allocation policy

A range is allocated in the cache every time the frontend encounters a cache miss while performing a range query. Our profiling data (e.g., Figure 4) suggests that most fetches are not double fetches, hence we expect frequent range allocations in the cache. Our custom allocator helps reduce the pressure on the (less efficient) underlying allocator, because many ranges can be allotted from the same region buffer.

Allocating ranges entails creating metadata and data objects in the appropriate regions. To this end, the backend uses a `region` accounting structure, which keeps track of all buffers allotted to the referent region. To speedup object creation, the `region` accounting structure stores a pointer to a region head buffer and favors servicing allocations from this buffer. As region heads get depleted at some point, new buffers are added to the region when appropriate and region heads get updated.

If an object cannot be created from the region head, the Cache Backend goes on the slow path iterating over all buffers allotted to the region until it finds one with enough space to service the request. As shown in Figure 6, some syscalls can transfer large amounts of user data, thus it is possible that a region can hold many depleted buffers. While this is more likely for *data* regions, it can also occur for *metadata* regions when syscalls execute many fetches. To optimize the slow path, the `region` accounting structure keeps a `freelist` containing only the buffers that are not yet depleted and can still service allocations. Lastly, if an object cannot be serviced on the slow path, then the backend leverages the custom allocator to create a new buffer in the referent region.

Figure 8: Heatmap showing the total amount of user data fetched by fetch-heavy syscalls.

Cache invalidation policy

When a system call terminates, all ranges currently held in the cache can be deallocated. As a result, one could relinquish all storage held by cached ranges on syscall exit. This strategy reduces the memory footprint and also yields a simple deallocation path flushing all the buffers held by metadata and data regions. Moreover, as discussed, syscalls do not fetch many ranges, thus on average we need not free many buffers. However, as shown in Figure 7, our profiling data shows that 99.6% of the processes that incur fetches do so across at least two syscalls. In other words, if a process issues a syscall that fetches user data, it is likely to issue other syscalls that do the same.

Given our profiling results, it may be tempting to preserve all the allocated region buffers across syscalls. However, while this strategy minimizes the number of calls to the underlying allocator (improving performance), it may also significantly increase the steady-state memory footprint. That is particularly the case for threads issuing syscalls that fetch a lot of user data (even more than 8 pages, as shown in Figure 6). Given these observations, our cache invalidation policy is to preserve the head buffers, for both metadata and data regions, across the syscalls of a given thread but release all the other buffers held by each region, on syscall exit. Additionally, on each syscall exit, we invalidate the bookkeeping structure used by our frontend when performing range queries. Finally, on thread exit we release the residual head buffers.

Cache initialization policy

Given that our two head buffers persist across syscalls of the same thread, the next question is when to allocate such buffers. An option would be to simply allocate the head buffers at thread

(i.e., `task_struct`) creation time. However, as shown in Figure 4, syscalls rarely fetch user data, e.g., $\approx 64\%$ of the syscalls do not issue any fetches. Hence, eager head buffer allocation at thread creation time may lead to unnecessary memory overhead. As a result, the backend allocates the two head buffers (and the two regions) *lazily*, on the first user fetch that a thread incurs.

Zero-copy optimization

Given that most syscalls fetch little data, storing data into the cache is generally inexpensive. However, some syscalls are fetch-heavy and copy large amounts of data. In such scenarios, copying data into the cache incurs a nontrivial cost (as shown later in our evaluation), so it is desirable to eliminate as many such extra copies as possible. To investigate optimization avenues, we isolated all syscalls in our profiling results that copy more than a page of data from user space. Figure 8 presents our results in a heatmap.

As shown in the figure, many of these syscalls (with the exception of `exec`) are I/O bound. To avoid resource contention, I/O bound syscalls rely on the kernel `iov_iterator` functionality to copy dozens of large chunks of user data into kernel staging buffers. Such buffers (and their copied data) persist unchanged until the hardware (e.g., network card, hard disk) becomes available to complete the I/O transfer. To optimize out expensive copies to the cache, we use the kernel staging buffer itself as a data cache for all the `iov_iterator` copies fetching one or more pages. To delay deallocation of such staging buffers until syscall exit, we increase the reference count on the underlying pages. When enabling this *zero-copy* optimization (SafeFetch default), our cache invalidation policy also releases the staging buffers on syscall exit.

3.7 Interconnection/Interfaces

SafeFetch can be used as a standalone tool to harden a target Linux kernel. To build a SafeFetch-enabled kernel, one can execute the following commands:

```
$ git clone git@github.com:vusec/safefetch.git safefetch
$ make -C safefetch mrproper
$ make -C safefetch x86_64_defconfig
$ cd safefetch && ./scripts/config -d CONFIG_AUDITSYSCALL -e
  CONFIG_SAFEFETCH && cd ..
$ make -C safefetch
$ sudo make -C safefetch install
```

To enable SafeFetch at run time, one can execute the following commands:

```
# enable syscall hooks for metadata/data management
$ ./safefetch_control.sh -hooks

# enable safefetch in adaptive mode
$ ./safefetch_control.sh -adaptive 4096 4096 0

# disable safefetch
$ ./safefetch_control.sh

# enable safefetch in rbtree mode
$ ./safefetch_control.sh -rbtree 4096 4096 0
```

For more information, see <https://github.com/vusec/safefetch>.

3.8 Related Work

While double-fetch or TOCTTOU (Time-of-Check-to-Time-of-Use) vulnerabilities affect different interfaces and components (e.g., enclaves [10, 27], sandboxes [52], compilers [76], and compartments [5]), we focus here on closely related research on operating system kernels. Serna[64] was the first who coined the name “*double-fetch vulnerability*” to describe an instance in the Windows kernel. Since then, research has focused on finding double-fetch bugs (through static and dynamic program analysis) or even mitigating these issues.

Static analysis

On the static analysis front, Wang et al.[71] leverages pattern matching analysis on source code to find double-fetch bugs in the Linux kernel. DFTinker[49] extends such pattern-based approach to increase double-fetch coverage and reduce false positives. While pattern-matching techniques proved effective in uncovering new double-fetch bugs, they still produce a high rate of false positives and negatives and are fundamentally limited to detecting only specific bug patterns.

DEADLINE[78] and DFTracker[72] improve static detection of double fetches by means of compiler-level symbolic execution. While these approaches can be applied more broadly (e.g., to detect compiler-induced double fetches[75, 77]) and are generally better suited for vetting false positives, symbolic execution introduces other limitations (e.g., path explosion) and does not completely remove false reporting (e.g., due to imprecise memory modeling or incomplete code coverage). DEADLINE, for example, does not detect double fetches in inline assembly, which is widely used in the kernel.

Dynamic analysis

On the dynamic analysis front, Jurczyk and Coldwind [39] propose Bochspwn, which instruments memory access callbacks in an x86 emulator to trace double-fetch patterns. Coupled with fuzzing, their technique found a series of exploitable double fetches in the Windows kernel. However, Bochspwn incurs high overheads because its tracing instrumentation affects the emulator’s fast path. Wilhelm [75] uses a similar approach to Bochspwn and found double-fetch vulnerabilities in the Xen hypervisor, one of which was introduced through compiler optimizations. Schwarz et al. [63] use a fuzzer in conjunction with concurrent user memory accesses to detect double fetches through a cache covert channel. However, such a solution is reliant on hardware features (e.g., caches), which vary across microarchitectures and are subject to noise. While dynamic techniques are often more precise than static approaches, they are fundamentally subject to code coverage and limited to finding double-fetch bugs only on executed code paths.

Mitigations

Midas [8] is the first proposed mitigation to protect the operating system kernel against double-fetch vulnerabilities. Midas relies on MMU-enabled Copy-on-Write semantics to create snapshots of user pages accessed by the kernel during syscall execution. As a result, Midas incurs nontrivial runtime performance overhead due to the cost of trapping/remapping and the coarse (page-granular) write interposition mechanism. Additionally, Midas whitelists some syscalls, most notably the fetch-heavy *exec* syscall. In contrast, SafeFetch eliminates the need for MMU-based instrumentation and offers comprehensive and efficient protection. Moreover, our solution is simple and seamlessly integrates with existing kernel code paths. Indeed, SafeFetch’s high-level design is inspired by the “*kernel-side caching of user space memory*” on the wishlist of Linux kernel developers to address double-fetch vulnerabilities [45].

4 FATex

This section explores the architecture, implementation, evaluation results, and interconnections of Quick Emulator (QEMU) with FIRMADYNE and Firmware Analysis Toolkit (FAT) extended (FATex), providing a detailed overview of its capabilities and how it contributes to the broader firmware analysis landscape.

4.1 Architecture

The FATex is an open-source tool designed for analyzing embedded firmware. Its architecture is modular, consisting of several components that each handle a specific aspect of firmware analysis. The primary modules include:

- **Firmware Extraction:** FATex extracts the firmware from device images, such as raw binary files or firmware update packages.
- **Static Analysis:** This component analyzes the firmware statically by identifying the underlying architecture, reverse engineering the binaries, and extracting strings or potential vulnerabilities.
- **Dynamic Analysis:** FATex also includes support for dynamic analysis through emulation or running the firmware on virtualized platforms.
- **Report Generation:** After analysis, the toolkit generates detailed reports that summarize the findings, including potential vulnerabilities, exploitable weaknesses, and other critical information.

FATex utilizes other tools in its ecosystem such as Binwalk [60] for generic firmware extraction, QEMU [30] and FIRMADYNE [12] for emulation and dynamic analysis, and Binare's Platform API static and dynamic analysis endpoints intended for firmware extraction, SBOM recovery and vulnerability discovery and mapping. This combination allows for a comprehensive approach to firmware analysis. Its open-source nature allows for easy extension, enabling developers to customize or add new features to the toolkit.

4.2 Implementation

FATex is implemented primarily in Python, leveraging various open-source libraries and external tools to extend its functionality. Key implementation features include:

- **Firmware Extraction:** FATex currently integrates Binwalk to unpack firmware images, which enables it to identify file systems and embedded components. FATex also uses libarchive for extracting compressed firmware files. In mid-term planning also is to add Binare's Platform API endpoint calls/integration for further support of firmware extraction.

- **Static Analysis:** The toolkit leverages various static analysis techniques, including disassembly of firmware binaries using tools like Ghidra [53] or Radare2 [57]. FATex also incorporates string extraction and hashing methods to identify known vulnerabilities or configurations. In mid-term planning also is to add Binare's Platform API endpoint calls/integration for further support of static analysis, SBOM and software components information recovery, and subsequent mapping to vulnerability and licensing information.
- **Dynamic Analysis:** Through integration with QEMU, FATex provides dynamic analysis of firmware by emulating the firmware's environment and identifying runtime vulnerabilities.
- **Report Generation:** After performing the analysis, FATex generates reports that summarize detected vulnerabilities, including detailed information about potential attack surfaces. The reports are formatted in a human-readable form, often supported by various output formats like HTML, CSV, or JSON for easy integration into larger analysis workflows. In mid-term planning also is to add Binare's Platform API endpoint calls/integration for further support of enhanced report generation specific to FATex results.

4.3 Evaluation Results

FATex has been evaluated in various settings, including analysis of publicly available firmware images and proprietary firmware from IoT devices.

The tool is currently undergoing evaluation, and development extension. The evaluation process involves running the tool, extracting the binary file, and assigning it an IP address. Once the IP address is accessible to dynamic testing tools (e.g, network scanners, web penetration testing, fuzzers, etc.), the produced dynamic analysis and testing artefacts will be collecting (e.g., screenshot captured and converted to base64 format for Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) vulnerabilities, filesystem logs for system commands, etc.). Overall, this will produce a directory of file(s) containing the results of the tests that will further be encoded into JSON as inline content ready for the creation of the corresponding DSCG and TBOM files.

4.4 Interconnection/Interfaces

FATex is designed to be easily integrated with other tools and workflows, offering several interfaces for interoperability:

- **Command Line Interface (CLI):** The primary way to interact with FATex is through its CLI, which allows users to run firmware extraction, static analysis, dynamic analysis, and reporting tasks. The CLI supports various options and parameters for fine-tuning the analysis process.
- **Integration with Binwalk:** FATex relies heavily on Binwalk for firmware extraction and analysis, integrating seamlessly with it to extract files and identify embedded components.

- **Quick Emulator (QEMU) for Dynamic Analysis:** FATex integrates with QEMU to emulate the firmware on virtualized platforms for dynamic analysis, enabling the execution of firmware in a controlled environment to detect runtime vulnerabilities.
- **Extensibility:** Given its open-source nature, FATex allows users to extend its functionality by developing new modules or integrating it with other security tools. It supports integration with other static and dynamic analysis tools, providing a flexible framework for comprehensive firmware evaluation.
- **Integration with Binare's Platform:** As RESCALE platform matures, FATex will also be enriched with integrations/calls to Binare's Platform endpoints for the purpose of improving and enriching the results from the basic FATex flows.

By offering these interconnections and interfaces, FATex ensures that it can be easily incorporated into broader security workflows, such as automated vulnerability scanning, and enables it to function within larger security testing platforms.

5 InSpectre Gadget

As the community slowly comes to grips with various forms of transient execution attacks [41, 46, 50, 43, 3, 74], Spectre v2 or Branch Target Injection (BTI) [15] remains one of the most severe ones, able to transiently divert the control flow of a program. If attackers can find a snippet of code that encodes secret data into the microarchitectural state, i.e., a (disclosure) *gadget*, they can force a victim program, e.g., the kernel, to transiently jump to it. Even in the face of hardware mitigations such as eIBRS, researchers have shown that Spectre v2 can still leak secret data across privilege levels on Intel systems through what is known as Branch History Injection (BHI) [3].

However, neither academia [3] nor industry [37] ever found an exploitable “*native*” gadget and the only existing exploit relies on a gadget injected by the authors themselves using eBPF. Since then, new advanced mitigations such as Indirect Branch Tracking (IBT) and its recent fine-grained counterpart FineIBT, have reduced the set of usable gadgets even (much) further. As a result, it is a common belief that deployed mitigations such as eIBRS and privileged eBPF (now default in all popular Linux distributions) are sufficient to eliminate the cross-privilege Spectre-v2 attack surface—and even more so in combination with the opt-in IBT or FineIBT mitigations.

To challenge this belief, our key observation is that current techniques to identify such gadgets either *overfit* “standard” patterns—identifying only gadgets that look like a handful of known Spectre examples and ignoring less conventional patterns—or grossly *overapproximate*—identifying many *potential* gadgets of which exploitability is highly uncertain. Examples of the latter are approaches that identify gadgets based on their high-level data flow, leaving exploitability to manual analysis [3, 38, 32]. Examples of the former include all pattern-based gadget scanners [58, 54, 56], but also all simplifying and self-limiting gadget definitions [37]. Overly constraining the definition of a gadget is dangerous, because even snippets that do not meet all the preconditions of a standard gadget can still leak data with advanced exploitation techniques [32, 38, 74]—leaving a gap between what attackers need for exploitation and what vendors and developers consider for mitigation.

To address these issues, we present *InSpectre Gadget*, an in-depth Spectre gadget inspector that uses symbolic execution to accurately reason about exploitability of usable gadgets. To this end, our tool explicitly models data *constraints* and knowledge of advanced *exploitation techniques*. This strategy relaxes the common preconditions of standard gadgets, while still avoiding the common overapproximations that would otherwise report many unexploitable gadgets. Moreover, it provides the analyst with insights into exploitability characteristics, such as the exploitation techniques required, the constraints to be met, the values that can be leaked, etc. We applied InSpectre Gadget to the Linux kernel and found exploitable gadgets that allowed us to implement the first *native* Spectre-v2 exploit against the Linux kernel on last-generation Intel CPUs. Our exploit is based on the BHI variant and is able to leak kernel memory eBPF.

Contributions

To summarize our contributions:

1. We build InSpectre Gadget, a gadget inspector that evaluates exploitability of potential gadgets, incorporating data constraints and knowledge of advanced exploitation techniques.
2. We applied InSpectre Gadget to the Linux kernel and found exploitable gadgets to implement the first native (no-eBPF) BHI exploit on the latest Linux kernel and last-generation Intel CPUs.
3. We disclosed our findings to Intel and other affected vendors, which assigned a CVE (CVE-2024-2201) to “Native” BHI and deployed mitigations.

5.1 Background

This section provides background information on transient execution attacks as well as recent Spectre-v2 attacks and defenses.

5.1.1 Transient Execution Attacks

Modern CPUs rely on a multitude of speculation mechanisms to achieve better performance. For example, whenever a CPU encounters a control flow instruction like a conditional branch or an indirect branch, the correct target might not be known yet. To avoid stalling, the CPU uses a set of internal structures, called *predictors*, to determine the next instruction to fetch, and starts *speculatively* executing instructions. If the speculation is later revealed to be incorrect, the CPU will undo the effects of the *transient* execution and restart from the correct jump target. However, traces of the transient computation can still be observed in the shared microarchitectural state, e.g. in the cache. An attacker can then measure these traces with techniques such as FLUSH+RELOAD [79] and PRIME+PROBE [47] and recover the values of registers and memory used during the transient computation.

5.1.2 Spectre v2

In 2018, the disclosure of Spectre [41] famously demonstrated how speculation can be used to leak data across security domains. One variant presented in the paper, originally known as Spectre v2 or Branch Target Injection (BTI), shows how speculation of indirect branches can be used to transiently divert the control flow of a program and redirect it to an attacker-chosen location. The attack works by poisoning one of the CPU predictors, the Branch Target Buffer (BTB), which is used to decide where to jump on indirect branch speculation. Initially, mitigations were proposed at the software level and, later, in-silicon mitigations such as Intel eIBRS [16] and ARM CSV2 [2] were added to newer generations of CPUs to isolate predictions across privilege levels.

Figure 9: **The BHI attack.** The attacker first triggers the branch C_A with history H_A ①, which inserts the target T_A into the BTB ②, then triggers the victim branch C_V with history H_V ③. The histories are crafted so that C_A and C_V share the same BTB entry, so from C_V the CPU speculates to T_A ④.

5.1.3 Branch History Injection

In 2022, Branch History Injection (BHI) [3] showed that, despite mitigations, cross-privilege Spectre v2 is still possible on latest Intel CPUs by poisoning the Branch History Buffer (BHB). Figure 9 provides a high-level overview of the attack.

In summary, by executing a sequence of conditional branches (H_A and H_V) right before performing a system call, an unprivileged attacker can cause the CPU to transiently jump to a chosen target (T_A) when speculating over an indirect call in the kernel (C_V). This happens because the CPU picks the speculative target for C_V from a shared structure, the BTB, that is indexed using both the address of the instruction *and the history* of previous conditional branches, which is stored in the Branch History Buffer (BHB). Finding the right combination of histories that will result in a collision can be done with brute-forcing.

To ensure the injected target, T_A , contains a disclosure gadget, the original BHI attack relied on the presence of the extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF), through which an unprivileged user can craft code that lives in the kernel.

5.1.4 Defenses

As a recommended mitigation for BHI, Intel has advised to disable unprivileged eBPF, which is now disabled by default in the Linux kernel, and to mitigate potential disclosure gadgets by prepending a LFENCE instruction to them[18].

Attack Surface Analysis

The original BHI paper presented an initial estimate of the BHI attack surface beyond eBPF using simple data-flow analysis and a loose definition of disclosure gadget [3]. The analysis pinpointed 1,177 *potential* gadgets in the Linux kernel, but with no insights into their exploitability. Later, Intel researchers statically analyzed the Linux kernel [37], adopting a more refined data-flow-based approach and finding an order of magnitude more potential gadgets. Again, with the analysis unable to automatically reason over exploitability, Intel researchers resorted to manually assessing exploitability of the 8 simplest (linear) gadgets. No gadgets were deemed exploitable (6 due to reachability issues, 2 due to leakage constraints). Ultimately, with many potential gadgets uncovered by both scanners but no evidence of practical exploitability, no additional mitigations were deployed.

Hardware mitigations

On the hardware front, Intel has proposed a hardware mitigation, the BHI_DIS_S indirect predictor control, which prevents the CPU from selecting BTB entries based on history coming from lower security domains. As the performance overhead is nontrivial, future CPUs might come with an optimized version, namely BHI_NO. At the time of writing, while Alder Lake and Raptor Lake Intel CPUs support BHI_DIS_S after applying a microcode update, the Linux Kernel does not have support to enable this feature.

Advanced software mitigations

Additional software mitigations, like Retpoline [17] or a software BHB-clearing sequence [18], have been proposed as spot fixes. However, they come with a prohibitive performance cost, discouraging practical deployment. For Linux, in particular, the software BHB-clearing sequence recommended by Intel has not been implemented at all, as developers rely on unprivileged eBPF being “the only known real-world BHB attack vector” [26].

IBT

Indirect Branch Tracking (IBT) [66] is a defense for code-reuse attacks, such as return-oriented programming [65] and jump-oriented programming [9], which ensures that indirect branches always jump to an intended target. Intel CPUs implement a coarse-grained version of IBT in hardware, which ensures that every indirect branch lands on a special instruction (endbr32 or endbr64), which has to be inserted by the compiler. While IBT was originally designed to address architectural control-flow hijacking, it is also part of Intel’s mitigation guidance for BHI [18]. This is to provide defense-in-depth against speculative control-flow hijacking, limiting—somewhat similarly to the existing eIBRS—the possible Spectre-v2 disclosure gadget locations to the beginning of *any* indirect branch target in the kernel. Support for IBT was added to Intel processors with the Tiger Lake series [14] and is enabled by default from Linux kernel v6.2 [13].

FineIBT

Researchers have recently proposed a finer-grained IBT variant in software, called FineIBT [31]. The idea is to instrument the caller of each IBT-guarded indirect call to load a unique value into a register as well as the callee to check said value. If the value is different from the expected one, the execution path is directed to an illegal instruction to abort execution.

This further restricts indirect calls to (architecturally or speculatively) target only compliant callees. Support for FineIBT was recently introduced in Linux kernel v6.2 [80]. Since FineIBT relies on Clang-instrumented kernels [31], to our knowledge, it is not yet enabled by default in any Linux distribution (unlike its IBT building block).

5.2 Threat Model

We consider a traditional cross-privilege Spectre-v2 threat model, with a local unprivileged attacker seeking to disclose information from a privileged victim, such as the operating system kernel or the hypervisor. We specifically focus on a victim Linux kernel, running with all default Spectre-v2 mitigations on last-generation Intel CPUs such as eIBRS [16] and privileged eBPF. Finally, we assume other classes of vulnerabilities (e.g., memory errors) are subject of orthogonal mitigations and not part of the attack surface under study.

5.3 Overview

To perform a Spectre-v2 attack against the kernel on last-generation Intel systems, one must target an indirect branch in the kernel that jumps to a disclosure gadget. Using BHI, one can then speculatively hijack a victim branch to the chosen gadget. InSpectre Gadget aids the analyst in choosing a suitable gadget, following the workflow depicted in Figure 10.

As shown in the figure, the analyst provides InSpectre Gadget with a kernel image and a list of candidate gadgets in input. Our tool inspects each candidate for a fixed number of basic blocks with symbolic execution and returns a list of gadgets that lead to the transmission of a secret. Along with the gadgets, our tool outputs a number of gadget characteristics: the advanced exploitation techniques required (if any), the constraints that have to be met, the registers that have to be controlled, and the values that can be leaked. Such characteristics are stored into a database, which the analyst can later filter according to what targets are reachable, what registers are controlled when the speculative hijack happens, and what mitigations are enabled for a given target. The resulting gadgets can then be exploited to mount end-to-end Spectre-v2 kernel attacks.

In the next sections, we first elaborate on how InSpectre Gadget models gadgets (constraints, exploitability, etc.) and how it then performs exploitation-aware gadget inspection.

Figure 10: **InSpectre gadget workflow.** The analyst provides a kernel image and a list of target addresses to InSpectre Gadget ①, which performs in-depth inspection to find gadgets that can leak secrets and output their characteristics. The gadgets can be filtered ② based on the available attacker-controlled registers and the mitigations enabled, and used to craft Spectre-v2 exploits against the kernel ③.

5.4 InSpectre Gadget

A recurring problem in transient execution attacks is evaluating if a given instruction sequence can leak a secret via a—typically cache [79, 47, 34, 1, 55, 42]—covert channel. To leak a secret through the cache, an attacker needs to open a *speculation window* and accommodate a *disclosure gadget*. In this section, we explain that practical disclosure gadgets extend well beyond those that fit existing narrow definitions. Next, we show how InSpectre Gadget uses symbolic execution to analyze the candidate gadgets for Spectre-v2 exploitability.

5.4.1 Standard Gadgets

Today’s tools typically concentrate on finding speculation windows and overapproximating exploitability—leaving the analysis of disclosure gadgets to the human analyst. Unfortunately, the complexity of such exploitability analysis is daunting and, unsurprisingly, analysts generally look for *standard* Spectre disclosure gadgets, such as the one in Listing 1.

```

1 // Load from attacker-controlled address
2 uint64_t secret = *attacker;
3 // Mask the loaded value
4 uint8_t secretByte = (secret | & 0xFF);
5 // Shift the result

```

```
6  uint32_t tsecret = secretByte << 9;
7  // Use transmission secret as index.
8  uint64_t transmission = *(tbase + tsecret);
```

Listing 1: Standard Spectre disclosure gadget.

In a standard (or “perfect”) gadget, the CPU loads a *secret* from an attacker-controlled address. The loaded secret must be sufficiently small, either by nature, or as the result of a bitmask (Line 4), to serve as an index into a second buffer—ideally shared with the attacker. This second buffer is known as the **reload buffer**. Moreover, to ensure that each value of the secret corresponds to a different cache line, the gadget should *shift* the value left by some stride (Line 6). The result is known as the *transmitted secret*. As the gadget subsequently adds it to a second attacker-controlled value which we refer to as the *transmission base* and dereferences the resulting value, it inadvertently establishes a **transmission** through a cache covert channel. Specifically, by iterating over the reload buffer with the same stride while timing the accesses, attackers can infer that the secret value is the index of the buffer element for which the access is fast (because it is in the cache).

5.4.2 Exploitation-Aware Gadget Analysis

Standard gadgets are the most intuitive to understand and the most straightforward to exploit, but they are by no means the only exploitable ones. While limiting the analysis to standard gadgets reduces the complexity, attackers are under no obligation to respect such restrictions. BLINDSIDE [32], KASPER [38], PACMAN [59], and RETBLEED [74], for example, all exploit gadgets that deviate from such narrow definitions. Moreover, besides leaking information through the cache, attackers may avail themselves of a myriad of other covert channels [33, 62, 29, 7, 61]. In this section, we relax the assumptions for standard gadgets, describe the additional challenge posed by each relaxation, and where appropriate, explain how we can meet the challenge and still leak secrets.

C1. Base not controlled

To perform FLUSH+RELOAD an attacker needs to be in control not only of the secret address, but also of the transmission base, so that the transmission load falls inside of the reload buffer. However, if the base is not controlled, attackers can still perform PRIME+PROBE [47].

C2. Secret entropy too big

If the code does not mask the secret prior to its transmission, the entropy impedes its recovery by the attacker who would have to probe too many memory locations. However, if the attackers control the transmission base, they can still exploit such gadgets by repurposing a technique pioneered in earlier attacks [32, 62, 74], which we call the *known-prefix* technique. First, the attacker chooses a location in memory near the secret that contains a small known value, and uses that as the secret address. Then, by increasingly shifting the address, the attacker makes

Figure 11: **Known-prefix technique.** The attacker first points the secret address to some known data ①. Then, by shifting the address ②, small portions of the secret are revealed. With that, one can adjust the base of subsequent transmissions ③.

sure that only a few bytes of the secret are unknown at any given transmission, and adjusts the transmission base according to the bytes that are already known (see Figure 11).

C3. Max secret too high

Another problem that may occur when leaking a large secret value is that the transmission address might end up outside the valid address space. However, if enough bits of the transmission base are under attacker control, one can adjust the base to overflow the secret value, ensuring that the transmission always occurs in the valid address space. We call this technique *base adjusting* and it is often used in conjunction with the known-prefix technique.

C4. Secret too small

If the gadget does not shift the secret value prior to transmission, the lower bits cannot be recovered through cache covert channels, since nearby addresses belong to the same cache line. However, if at least one byte of the secret is above cache-line granularity, we can use the known-prefix technique to leak the uppermost byte in each iteration. Otherwise, an attacker may use the *sliding* technique of RETBLEED [74], which exploits the fact that prefetchers generally do not prefetch cache lines across pages [67]. An attacker may now adjust the base address to be near a page boundary, so that even a one-bit difference in the secret value will result in the transmission being observed on another memory page. Doing so eliminates any cache and prefetcher noise that would otherwise make two different values indistinguishable.

C5. Base aliasing

In some cases, even if the transmission base is attacker-controlled, the base cannot be chosen without influencing the secret address—a phenomenon we refer to as *aliasing*. This may occur, for instance, if the base is computed from a value that is also used to compute the secret address. In this case, an attacker can still leak values using PRIME+PROBE. However, not all secret addresses may be targeted as the probe region must reside within mapped memory. Specifically, since the probe region typically follows the secret address, the final secret addresses result in a non-mapped probe region. Other, more complex dependencies between the base and the secret address out of scope. InSpectre Gadget marks these cases as not (easily) exploitable.

C6. Non-linear gadgets

An implicit assumption of most static analysis techniques for gadget scanning is that all the instructions have to be in the same basic block. Since modern CPUs all support nested speculation, this is not a limitation in practice. The attacker can either train branches or simply use static prediction to ensure that the transmission gadget is reached during speculative execution. An attacker can also use SMT contention, as demonstrated by prior work [51], to delay branch resolution and create large speculation windows that can accommodate multiple basic blocks.

C7. Other transmitters

Finally, a plethora of covert channels exist in modern CPUs outside of caches (e.g., the TLB [48]) and one should flexibly support different transmitters. For brevity, we focus our main analysis on classic secret-dependent data load/store transmitters and later show our tool can be easily extended to support other vectors such as the recent SLAM covert channel [36].

5.4.3 Design

While advanced exploitation techniques relax the assumptions for standard gadgets, each has its own requirements and constraints for applicability. To reason over the constraints and to assess if the code satisfies them, InSpectre Gadget employs *symbolic execution*—expressing variables as *symbols*, and exploring all the possible directions of a program’s control flow at the same time, while recording the corresponding *symbolic constraints*. To this end, we build our tool on top of ANGR[68], a symbolic execution engine widely used in the field of software security and reverse engineering.

Although symbolic execution quickly leads to *state explosion* in the general case, InSpectre Gadget explores only a small fraction of the program’s control flow. In particular, since the number of instructions executed during a speculation window is limited, symbolic execution can easily explore multiple paths, while keeping the number of explored states small. All the steps described below are performed automatically by InSpectre Gadget.

Tracking attacker control

We start our analysis by substituting all the values stored in registers and on the stack with symbolic variables, which for now we assume are *attacker-controlled*, and marked as such. Next, we symbolically execute code starting from a given location. On each load, we produce a new symbolic value with a label attached to it. If the load comes from an attacker-controlled symbol, it is marked as a *potential secret*. If the address comes from a potential secret, it is marked as a *potential transmission*. Note that *potential secret* implies *attacker-controlled*, since it is any value loaded from an attacker-chosen location. Similarly, *potential transmission* implies *potential secret*. This strategy allows us to track of attacker control through complex chains of loads.

Store-to-Load Forwarding

We model Store-To-Load Forwarding by keeping a list of all the symbolic stores, and checking this list for each of the loads encountered by the symbolic execution engine. If the symbolic expression of the load address aliases with that of a previous store, we forward the stored value to the load. Store-to-Load forwarding can be enabled or disabled with a runtime flag.

Potential transmissions

We let the symbolic execution engine run for a configurable number of basic blocks, recording all the constraints that might be added, for instance by `cmove` or `branch` instructions. We also record the symbolic expression of each load. Finally, after the scanning phase is finished, the scanner reports a list of potential transmissions, i.e., loads whose symbolic address has been marked as a potential secret.

In a second phase, we inspect the AST of the symbolic expression of each potential transmission, identifying the transmission base, transmitted secret, and secret address. A high-level example is shown in Figure 12. Finally, we check if the base depends on any value used to construct the secret address, perform a range analysis to infer the minimum, maximum and stride of all the transmission components, and perform an *inferable-bits* analysis to infer which bits of the secret end up in the transmission and at which position. This comprehensive analysis is crucial for accurate exploitability reasoning. For instance, data-flow information alone is insufficient to determine the controllability requirements to be met.

Gadget reasoning

With this information, we can finally reason about each gadget. All the properties found during the analysis, along with a list of registers that the attacker needs to control for each gadget, are saved in a database. We now use a *reasoner* to model exploitation techniques with database queries. The reasoner inserts columns indicating which gadgets can leak a secret, and, if needed, which techniques are required. For instance, if a gadget has a high secret entropy (i.e., number of transmitted bits > 16), the reasoner checks if we can perform the known-prefix technique (i.e., secret address is attacker-controlled with granularity ≤ 16 bits).

Figure 12: **Anatomy of a transmission.** Once a potential transmission is identified through symbolic execution, InSpectre Gadget dissects its symbolic expression into components, which are then analyzed to reason about exploitability.

5.4.4 Limitations

As opposed to tools like KASPER [38], InSpectre Gadget is designed to analyze only the content of *speculation windows* (e.g., call and jump targets for Spectre-v2), whose entry points have to be provided by the analyst. Other aspects needed for end-to-end exploitation, such as the *reachability* of the target and the presence of a suitable *victim branch*, are not part of the tool’s output. Moreover, InSpectre Gadget cannot completely prove the *absence* of gadgets in a given snippet of code.

Regarding exploitability results, our current prototype has a number of limitations potentially impacting accuracy. First, our tool is based on ANGR and relies on both its disassembler (CAPSTONE) and constraint solver (Z3). Whenever an error occurs in one of these components, e.g., on unsupported instructions, we have to bail out from the analysis, leaving some symbolic states unexplored. Second, transmissions that contain a complex symbolic expression, e.g., two independently-controlled loads used in a XOR operation, cannot be easily unpacked into a *base* and a *transmitted secret*, but might still leak a value. We mark these cases as **complex** and approximate their ranges by querying the SAT solver for the minimum and maximum values of the whole expression and of each sub-expression. We also use this approach when performing range analysis on expressions with complex (symbolic) constraints, whose values cannot be easily reduced to an interval or a small set. For these cases, besides reporting the minimum and the maximum values, we also check if certain bits are always 0 or 1 to approximate the stride.

Finally, at the moment our tool models the attacker’s control over complex chains of loads as a binary condition (*controlled* or *not controlled*), as opposed to reporting the degree of control as done for transmission components. For complex aliasing cases, this can introduce imprecision (e.g., inaccurate classification of the required exploitation techniques).

5.5 Interconnection/Interfaces

InSpectre Gadget can be used as a standalone tool—or easily integrate with other tools and workflows—in order to analyze the Spectre attack surface of an input program binary.

A typical workflow operates as follows:

```
# Analyze <CSV> targets for binary <BINARY>
$ inspectre analyze <BINARY> --address-list <CSV> --config
  config_all.yaml --output out  gadgets.csv --asm out/asm

# Perform exploitability analysis of any gadgets found
$ inspectre reason out/gadgets.csv out/gadgets-reasoned.csv
```

The workflow above generates a report of the form:

```
[-] Imported 32 gadgets
[-] Performing exploitability analysis...
    Found 2 exploitable gadgets!
[-] Saving to out/gadgets-reasoned.csv
[-] Done!
```

For more information, see <https://github.com/vusec/inspectre-gadget>.

5.6 Related Work

Spectre gadget scanners

Spectre gadget scanners documented in literature mostly focus on Spectre v1. With exceptions [58], such scanners typically rely on dynamic analysis. SPECFUZZ [54] uses fuzzing to detect out-of-bounds accesses on a speculative path. SpecFuzz marks every out-of-bound access as a gadget, without modeling attacker controllability. In response, SPECTAINT [56] requires the secret address to be tainted with attacker input, as determined via dynamic taint analysis (DTA). KASPER [38] also relies on DTA for gadget characterization, but generalizes the fixed patterns used by SpecTaint. Unlike InSpectre Gadget, all these solutions identify gadgets solely based on their data flow, an overapproximation that leaves their exploitability uncertain. Like ours, other gadget scanners are based on symbolic execution, but typically focus on other use cases (i.e., verification [35] or early detection [70]) with no exploitability analysis.

Spectre-v2 attacks

Besides work exclusively focusing on gadget scanning, prior Spectre-v2 attack efforts also described gadget analysis campaigns. For instance, the RETBLEED authors [74] used static data-flow analysis to identify basic 3-load gadgets for a native Spectre-RSB-to-BTI exploit. This simple strategy is sufficient as Retbleed exploits (similar to Inception [69]) vulnerable older-generation CPUs with no eIBRS. As such, they can speculatively hijack control flow to arbitrary code locations with no restriction.

The BHI authors [3], also using data-flow-based gadget analysis, presented evidence eBPF=off exploits were at least potentially feasible on modern eIBRS-enabled platforms—but with no

attempt to reason about exploitability. Intel later presented a similar gadget analysis campaign along with manual exploitability analysis of “the most promising” gadgets, reporting no exploitable ones [37]. This shows the difficulty of performing exploitability analysis—even from experts *manually* inspecting the gadgets—without a general framework to rule out self-limiting assumptions.

In contrast, by analyzing one (v2) transient window at the time, InSpectre Gadget can leverage the full power of symbolic execution to deeply characterize gadgets and reason about their exploitability for the first time, without running into the limitations of traditional symbolic execution tools [11, 25], such as scalability and state explosion. Crucially, our tool models knowledge of advanced exploitation techniques including sliding [74, 32] and gadget chaining [69, 6].

6 Main Innovations & Conclusion

This section concludes the deliverable by summarizing the key contributions and outlining future work within Task 3.4.

6.1 Main Innovations

Summarizing, this deliverable presented three key contributions:

- **SafeFetch**: a solution for detecting and mitigating double-fetch (software) vulnerabilities, which frequently affect low-level system components, such as operating system kernels.
- **FATex**: a generic tool designed to perform firmware analysis for the purpose of security testing.
- **InSpectre Gadget**: a solution for detecting and analyzing Spectre-type (hardware) vulnerabilities, which represent an increasingly large attack surface for low-level system components.

6.2 Conclusion

This deliverable outlined the outcome of the first phase of Task 3.4, “Low-Level System Security Testing”, focused on the initial design of the solutions for security testing of low-level system components. To this end, we focused on the core solutions targeting (i) high-impact vulnerabilities in the hardware/software stack and (ii) low-level system components such as operating system kernels, hypervisors, or firmware, whose integrity and confidentiality are crucial for system security.

On the software vulnerability front, we focused on double-fetch vulnerabilities and presented SafeFetch, an in-kernel memory cache to efficiently detect and mitigate these vulnerabilities. Linux kernel developers have already expressed interest in mainlining SafeFetch. At the firmware level, we also presented FATex, a generic firmware analysis platform for the purpose of security testing.

On the hardware vulnerability front, we focused on Spectre-type vulnerabilities and presented InSpectre Gadget, a program analysis tool to uncover Spectre gadgets in low-level system components and automatically determine their exploitability (and thus severity) properties. A number of organizations, such as Xen and Microsoft, have already adopted InSpectre Gadget for their internal attack surface analysis campaigns. Xen has also made contributions to the tool.

These efforts collectively provide a foundation for high-impact hardware/software vulnerability testing of low-level system components, complementing the other program analysis components of the RESCALE platform and contributing to the DSCG report established in Task 3.2 (and described in D3.3).

6.3 Future Work

In future work, we plan to expand the scope of our solutions, targeting additional vulnerabilities and components. In addition, we plan to conduct a thorough experimental evaluation across different targets. More specifically, for our three core solutions:

- **SafeFetch:** we plan to refine SafeFetch’s double-fetch vulnerability detector and conduct vulnerability-finding campaigns on different security boundaries.
- **FATex:** we plan to expand both RESCALE-relevant functional feature-set and our experimental evaluations to showcase the effectiveness of FATex in practice, with a particular aim to effectively and efficiently support RESCALES’s pilot demonstrator use-cases.
- **InSpectre Gadget:** we plan to expand the analysis operated by InSpectre Gadget and use the tool to conduct new attack surface analysis campaigns for other Spectre-type vulnerabilities.

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